

Reactivity-induced transients at the AKR-2 training and research reactor

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ABSTRACT

At the AKR-2 zero-power reactor operated at the TU Dresden, reactivity transients can be induced. In this study, five different transients are experimentally measured and simulated with the Monte Carlo (MC) code Serpent. These correspond to the individual drop of the three control rods, the simultaneous drop of all the control rods, and the reactor scram. This study investigates the applicability of the point reactor kinetics equation and deviations from the point kinetics formalism due to spatial effects resulting from detector location. The simulations presented use the nuclear data libraries ENDF/B-VIII.0 and JEFF-4.0. The control rod worths (CRWs) are determined by the prompt drop during the transients and compared to those of static simulations. The MC model quantitatively reproduces most of the experimental results. The necessity of investigating material and geometric data at the reactor, as well as the need for variance reduction techniques during transient MC simulations, are discussed as possible improvements for future transient activities.

Keywords: Reactivity transients, AKR-2 reactor, Serpent, Monte Carlo, Point kinetics

1. INTRODUCTION

Current efforts at the AKR-2 zero-power reactor at the TU Dresden aim to turn the facility into a benchmark platform for obtaining nuclear data and performing code validation. This objective is supported by the NAUTILUS research project [1]. Within this framework, the realization of high-quality experiments and detailed simulations are done. Recent investigations have demonstrated the applicability of the MC model developed with Serpent and MCNP for static simulations [2]. These include the integral and differential curves of the control rods, and the neutron spectrum in the experimental channels [3]. Other experiments, such as determining the reactor transfer function [4] and the Rossi-alpha value, demonstrate the applicability of the model in scenarios where kinetic parameters are relevant.

Reactor kinetic parameters play a fundamental role in reactivity-induced transients. The delayed neutron fraction, the neutron generation time, and the precursors decay constants form the core of the point-kinetics formalism [5]. This study focuses on analysing reactivity-induced transients at the AKR-2. This analysis exploits the dynamic capabilities of the MC code Serpent [6], which enables to simulate events such as the drop of control rods [7]. In this study, five different transients are investigated. These correspond to the individual drop of each of the three control rods, the simultaneous drop of all the control rods and the reactor scram. Special attention is devoted to the following aspects:

1. Applicability of the point kinetics (PK) formalism to the previously mentioned transients,
2. The relevance of detector position for comparison between experimental and simulated results,
3. Multiple nuclear data libraries (ENDF/B-VIII.0 and JEFF-4.0) results,
4. Determination of the CRWs using static simulations and the prompt drop approximation, and
5. Requirements for additional reactivity-induced transients.

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Section 2 of this manuscript provides a brief description of the AKR-2 reactor geometry, materials, and detector arrangement, as well as the experimental details of the transients. Section 3 is devoted to the AKR-2 Serpent model and simulation details. Section 4 presents time-dependent results at various detector positions, as well as PK results, which use both nuclear data libraries and CRW values. Section 5 discusses the conclusions and future work.

2. THE AKR-2 REACTOR TRANSIENTS

2.1. Reactor description

The AKR-2 is a thermal zero-power reactor operated between 0 and 2 W. Its core consists of two separable cylindrical sections made of plates of a homogeneous mixture of polyethylene and uranium dioxide. Three control rods, which are located in the graphite reflector region, are used to change the power and shut down the reactor. During shutdown, the lower core half falls 5 cm. The reactor also contains four experimental channels, multiple detectors, instrumentation and control devices, and one AmBe startup neutron source. Paraffin and concrete around the reflector region serve as radiation shielding materials.

Geometrical and material specifications are presented in figure 1 and table I. Further details can be seen in [2]. The three control rods were extracted to determine the geometrical and dynamic specifications of the rods. It was observed that rod 1 moves 37.5 cm, rod 2 moves 38.4 cm, and rod 3 moves 39.0 cm. It was found that the sheets of cadmium that are attached to the polyethylene blocks are not completely flat, but wavy. This is not modelled. Besides, the rod drop time was found to be around 0.5 seconds.

Figure 1. (Left) Reactor mock-up with main components. "Lower" and "Upper" refer to the lower and upper core halves, respectively. Control rod 1 and experimental channels 1-2, 3-4, and 5-6 can be seen. The neutron source, reflector region, paraffin, and concrete surround the reactor core. (Right) Control rod 1 is shown. The aluminium casing houses a polyethylene block with cadmium-attached sheets. These are indicated with dashed lines. An arrow delimited by the words "in" and "out" indicates the range of motion of the control rod.

Table I. Technical parameters of the AKR-2.

Parameter	
Core diameter (cm)	24.8 - 25.1
Core height (cm)	27.8
Enrichment (%)	19.8
Reflector density (g/cm ³)	1.69 - 1.75
Cd rods - sheet thickness (mm)	0.5
sheet width (cm)	1.75 (3), 2.75 (3)
sheet height (cm)	39.6 - 40.0

2.2. Transients description and measurement

Five different reactivity-induced transients were performed at the AKR-2. The temperature as indicated by the thermocouples at the reflector region was 25 °C. At this temperature, the reactor cannot be made critical, even with all the control rods out. Therefore, an auxiliary acrylic bar with a diameter of 1.2 cm and a length of 30 cm was placed in the central experimental channel to increase the reactivity. All the five transients were initiated when the reactor was critical at 2 W. The reactor was made critical in two different ways. For the transient of rod 1 drop, the rod 2 was used to achieve criticality while the rods 1 and 3 were fully out. For the other four transients, the rod 1 was used to make the reactor critical while the rods 2 and 3 were out. At the AKR-2, the rods move from 0 to 4,000 digits, where 0 digits indicate that the rod is fully inserted, and 4,000 digits indicates that the rod is fully withdrawn.

Three detectors were used during this experimental campaign. Two Helium-3 proportional counters, each equipped with two 1/2-inch diameter counter tubes, were placed in the experimental channels 3-4 and 5-6. The detectors were positioned in a way to reduce their dead time and to achieve a sufficiently high count rate. Additionally, a permanently mounted fission chamber, which is installed at the core level in the reflector region, was used. The location of the detectors and the acrylic bar in central channel 1-2 can be observed in figure 2. For the measured data, dead-time corrections and uncertainty estimates were obtained via bootstrapping of single neutron detection events.

3. TRANSIENTS SIMULATIONS

3.1. Overview

The Serpent MC code can perform static, burnup, and transient simulations. Two steps are required for transient simulations. First, a static simulation is performed to create the source with the neutron precursors and delayed neutrons distribution. During this phase, detectors are placed at multiple locations. In this work, they are located at the measurement positions (see figure 2). Additionally, an extra detector in the simulation is used to estimate the neutron density in the core throughout the transient. Due to its low statistical uncertainty, this detector serves as a reference for the transient simulation.

With the steady-state solution as the initial condition, the transient simulation is carried out to study the time-dependent response of the reactor. This is induced modifying the geometry or materials of the reactor. In particular, control rod drops and lower core half drop can be managed by geometrical transformations with constant speed or acceleration. The Serpent input cards *transv* and *transa* can be used. During the static phase, the k_{eff} of the system must be close to 1. To guarantee the correctness of the static simulation phase, the transient is run without any transformation during a short interval of time (some milliseconds) and it is verified that there is not change in the detector results.

Figure 2. (Left) Top view of the core level of the Serpent of the AKR-2 Serpent MC model. Detector locations are indicated in red. The two He-3 detectors in channels 3-4 and 5-6 and the fission chamber are displayed. The acrylic rod is inside of the central channel 1-2. An additional acrylic rod of 20 cm length was inserted (not shown here) for the transient of the insertion of all rods simultaneously to compare with JEFF-4.0 simulation results (see section 4). The inserted control rod 1 is shown in violet. (Right) The vertical section at the middle of the core is shown. The lower core half is in lowermost position; this occurs during the reactor shutdown.

3.2. The AKR-2 Serpent MC model

A detailed description of the model can be found in reference [2]. Most of the described simplifications are kept. A single value of 0.5 cm is used for the thickness of the cadmium sheet in the control rods. To induce reactivity-induced transients, the rods were dropped at a constant insertion speed using the card *transv*. The insertion time used in the translation is 500 ms. The lower core half drops within 280 ms, as measured by the reactor safety and control system. The nuclear data libraries used in this model are ENDF/B-VIII.0 and JEFF-4.0.

3.3. Modelling details

The simulations were performed at 298.15 K. The NJOY code was used to produce nuclear data, and the stochastic mixing approach was used to treat the thermal scattering laws interpolation. The position of the rod 1, 2, and 3 during the experiments and simulations can be seen in tables II and III. The critical position of rod 1 during the transient phase, when all rods are dropped simultaneously, differs between the two nuclear data libraries. Then, during the static phase of the JEFF-4.0 simulation, rod 1 was placed at 900 digits. Experimentally, the rod 1 was at 930 digits before inserting all rods. This ensured that k_{eff} during source generation was close to 1. Additionally, the *set keff* card is used to scale the fission neutron production, which affects both prompt and delayed neutrons [8]. During the static phase, 100,000 particles per cycle, 5,000 active, and 40 inactive cycles were done.

The AMD Ryzen 9 7950X 16-Core Processor was used with OpenMP parallelization and 32 OpenMP threads. To keep the statistical uncertainty below 1.5%, dynamic simulations were performed for the insertion of individual rods for around 194 hours, for the insertion of all rods for around 132 hours and

for the reactor scram for around 118 hours.

Table II. Rod positions during critical state in configuration for drop of rod 1 and k_{eff} .

	Experiment	ENDF/B-VIII.0	JEFF-4.0
Rod 1	4000	4000	4000
Rod 2	2788	2500	1100
Rod 3	4000	4000	4000
k_{eff}	~ 1	(1.00011 ± 0.00005)	(1.00010 ± 0.00005)

Table III. Rod positions during critical state in configuration for other four transients and k_{eff} .

	Experiment	ENDF/B-VIII.0	JEFF-4.0
Rod 1	2800/930*	2800	900
Rod 2	4000	4000	4000
Rod 3	4000	4000	4000
k_{eff}	~ 1	(1.00003 ± 0.00005)	(0.99985 ± 0.00005)

In table III, the *-symbol indicates the presence of a second acrylic rod in channel 1-2 in the experiment and simulation. The steady-stat is kept initially for 0.5 s. Then, rod and/or core drops occur. Time-dependent results are obtained for 9.5 s after the drops. Results at the core detector are obtained every 0.1 seconds, while results at the He-3 and fission chamber detectors are obtained every 0.25 seconds. A total of 200,000 particles were simulated per batch in the transient phase. The number of batches was determined to achieve a relative error smaller than 1.5 % in all the detectors at every time bin. The detector responses are (n,fission) in ^{235}U for the fission chamber and (n,p) in the He-3 detectors.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results for the transients proposed in section 2.2 using Serpent are presented in figures 3 and 4, along with the PK results. The proposed transients are qualitatively consistently modelled. Nevertheless, there are quantitative deviations from the experimental results, especially for the rod 1. The Serpent simulation slightly underestimates the prompt drop of the rods using both libraries in all cases. Geometric and material uncertainties in the control rod modelling are the reason for these deviations.

Table IV. Kinetic parameters during the static simulation phase.

Group i	$\beta_{\text{eff},i,\text{ENDF}}$ (pcm)	$\lambda_{\text{eff},i,\text{ENDF}}$ (s^{-1})	$\beta_{\text{eff},i,\text{JEFF}}$ (pcm)	$\lambda_{\text{eff},i,\text{JEFF}}$ (s^{-1})
1	27	0.0133	27	0.0125
2	141	0.033	116	0.0283
3	133	0.121	75	0.0425
4	296	0.303	156	0.133
5	122	0.850	258	0.292
6	51	2.855	72	0.666
7	-	-	64	1.643
8	-	-	19	3.554

To compare with the PK model, kinetic parameters are obtained using the iterated fission probability (IFP) method in Serpent. A six group structure of delayed neutrons and precursors were used in ENDF/B-VIII.0, while eight groups were used in the JEFF-4.0 results (see table IV). In the PK model, the

inserted reactivity profile was a linear ramp. Two eigenvalue simulations were used to determine the reactivity ramp, and the time span of the ramp was set equal to the time used during the translations in Serpent. The PK results can be seen as dashed blue lines in figures 3 and 4. The uncertainty band constitutes the upper and lower values of the PK model with considering 1σ in the eigenvalue simulations. It can be seen that the PK model agrees with the simulations if compared with detectors which are far

Figure 3. Rod 1, 2, and 3 transient simulations and experimental data (from top to bottom).

from the rod or structure dropped. It is worth to mention that the spatial dependence of the transients is resolved by the Serpent simulations. Both the Serpent simulations and the experimental data show:

- In rod 1 drop, a larger reduction of normalized counts occurs at the helium detectors with respect to the fission chamber. This is due to their proximity to the inserted rod. The largest reduction is observed in detector 1, which is the closest to the rod.
- In rod 2 drop, the helium detectors show similar behaviour as they are far from inserted rod 2. Instead, a larger reduction occurs in the fission chamber, which is the detector closest to the rod.

Figure 4. All rods insertion (top) and SCRAM (bottom) transient simulations and experimental data.

- In rod 3 drop, all the detectors' results evolve similarly. The rod is located far from the three detectors. Larger values in the simulated results using JEFF-4.0 library may result from the normalization of the time dependent data against the initial values before the rod is inserted.
- When all rods are inserted, a similar trend is observed in all the detectors. Simulations with both nuclear data libraries slightly underestimate the power decrease.
- During the reactor scram, the He detector 1 is slightly more reduced with respect to the others. This is due to its proximity to the reactor core. The fission chamber and the He detector 2 provide similar results. Experimentally, the prompt drop is around 10%, while in the simulation is 9%.

The CRWs are determined using two eigenvalue calculations and the prompt drop approximation, which is valid for small reactivity insertions ($\rho < 0.5\beta$). Firstly, the k_{eff} is computed for the three rods fully inserted and then for fully withdrawn. These eigenvalue simulations are done using 100,000 particles per cycle with 40 inactive cycles and 5,000 active cycles. To accomplish this, the asymptotic behaviours of the transients are extrapolated to the starts of the transients. Results are shown in figure 5.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In the framework of the NAUTILUS project and ongoing AKR-2 reactor benchmarking efforts, rod drop and shutdown transients were measured and simulated. The most updated Serpent model of the AKR-2 was used to accomplish this. The results for five reactivity-induced transients are shown using two different nuclear data libraries: ENDF/B-VIII.0 and JEFF-4.0. These were compared to the PK results. Special attention was given to the detector locations to highlight deviations from the PK formalism in both simulations and experiments. While the simulated transients reproduced these spatial effects, they underestimated the prompt drop in all cases. CRW was calculated using time-dependent data and static simulations to illustrate this discrepancy. The results indicate the need for a future sensitivity analysis to estimate uncertainty in simulated values due to unknown geometrical and material quantities of the

Figure 5. CRWs using static eigenvalue simulations and the prompt drop of experimental transients data (in red, green and blue) and simulations (shadows on experimental data) for multiple detectors.

control rods and lower core half. Future work will address the computational resources required to achieve low statistical uncertainty at the detector locations, implying use of variance reduction techniques. The extension of the research with dynamic Monte Carlo to larger systems is ongoing (see e.g. Ref. [7]). However, enormous computational resources and possibly consideration of multiphysics aspects are required, making it a difficult task.

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